

A RELIABILITY ANALYSIS OF LAMINATED COMPOSITES
AND CYLINDRICAL SHELLS

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ABSTRACT

A multilayer composite consisting of unidirectionally or orthogonally reinforced layers is under consideration. The scatter of the elastic constants and strength characteristics of a single layer is involved in the theoretical model. The reliability of a composite treated as a highly reliable system is calculated according to the concepts of the "weakest link" (the probabilistic version of the "first-ply-failure" approach) and the total loss of load-carrying capacity treated as the result of Markovian random layer-by-layer failure process. The results of application of the proposed methods to the reliability calculation of organic fibre/epoxy laminated cylindrical shells are briefly discussed.

INTRODUCTION

The following efficient approach [1] to the analysis of reliability of reinforced laminate structures can be used. A structure is divided into a finite number of elements (macro-volumes) each of them containing, in its turn, a great number of structural elements of a heterogeneous material (microvolumes). The macrovolume is selected under the assumption that the strain (stress) field generated under the load can be considered as statistically homogeneous. In many practically important cases, a lamina is assumed to be a macro-volume [2-6].

STOCHASTIC MODEL OF FIRST-PLY-FAILURE

We shall examine a multilayer packet consisting of uni-

directionally or orthogonally reinforced layers. The packet is subjected to the effect of the given tensor of forces $N_{\alpha\beta}(t)$ whose components are random functions of time. The quality of the j -th layer will be characterized by the three-dimensional vector:

$$\vec{\xi}^{(j)}(t) = \{ \xi_{11}^{(j)}(t), \xi_{22}^{(j)}(t), \xi_{12}^{(j)}(t) \},$$

where $\xi_{kl}^{(j)}$ are the components of the strain tensor related to the main axes of the j -th layer, which are random functions of time but do not depend on the spatial coordinates. The elastic and strength characteristics of the layer are random values with the specified distribution law.

Let it be that region Ω_j with a stochastic boundary is specified for the j -th layer in the three-dimensional strain space. The exit of the quality vector $\vec{\xi}^{(j)}(t)$ out of this region is regarded as failure of the layer. The probability of the event in which the vector $\vec{\xi}^{(j)}(t)$ does not leave the limits of the region Ω_j within the examined time period is determined as the reliability of the layer:

$$R_j(t) = P\{ \vec{\xi}^{(j)}(\tau) \in \Omega_j ; 0 \leq \tau \leq t \}. \quad (I)$$

In subsequent considerations, the examined multilayer packet is studied as a highly reliable system. Consequently, the probability (I) is expressed by means of the mathematical expectation of the number of intersections $\check{V}(\Gamma_j; t)$ per unit time by the trajectories $\vec{\xi}^{(j)}(t)$ of the surface Γ_j in the direction of the external normal to this surface using the relationship

$$R_j(t) = \exp\left[-\int_0^t \check{V}(\Gamma_j; \tau) d\tau\right]. \quad (2)$$

To calculate the reliability of the packet as a whole $R(t)$ the simplest approach based on the concept of the "weakest link" can be used. In this concept the function $R(t)$ is determined as the probability that the quality vector does not leave its corresponding limiting region in any of the N layers:

$$R(t) = \prod_{j=1}^N R_j(t). \quad (3)$$

To calculate the quantity $\check{V}(\Gamma_j; t)$, it is necessary

to specify the statistical characteristics of the external forces and the type of region of permissible states Ω_j . The scatter of the elastic constants and limiting strains of the single layer must be determined from the experiments on the specimens of composite material.

Let it be that the acting forces $N_{\alpha\beta}(t)$ are Gaussian random processes and can be represented in the form of a stochastically orthogonal spectral distribution:

$$N_{\alpha\beta}(t) = \langle N_{\alpha\beta}(t) \rangle + \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} Q_{\alpha\beta}(\omega) \exp(i\omega t) d\omega, \quad (4)$$

where the spectra $Q_{\alpha\beta}(\omega)$ satisfy the conditions of stochastic orthogonality:

$$\langle Q_{\alpha\beta}^*(\omega) Q_{\gamma\delta}(\omega') \rangle = S_{\alpha\beta, \gamma\delta}(\omega) \delta(\omega - \omega'). \quad (5)$$

Here and in subsequent considerations, the angular brackets indicate the operation of calculation of mathematical expectation; the asterisk denotes the transition to the complexly conjugated quantity; $\delta(\omega)$ is the delta function; $S_{\alpha\beta, \gamma\delta}(\omega)$ are the mutual spectral densities of the processes $N_{\alpha\beta}(t)$ and $N_{\gamma\delta}(t)$. The spectral densities are associated with the mutual correlation functions $K_{\alpha\beta, \gamma\delta}(t)$ by means of the relationships:

$$K_{\alpha\beta, \gamma\delta}(t) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} S_{\alpha\beta, \gamma\delta}(\omega) \exp(i\omega t) d\omega. \quad (6)$$

It should be mentioned that the random processes $N_{\alpha\beta}(t)$ are not stationary in the general case because $\langle N_{\alpha\beta}(t) \rangle$ may be arbitrary functions of time.

Let it be that the main direction of elasticity of the j -th layer I forms the angle φ_j with the direction of the coordinate axis x . Then, the components of the strain tensor in the main axes of the layer may be written in the form

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon_{\kappa\ell}^{(j)}(t) = & G_{\kappa\ell, xx}(A_{mn}, \varphi_j) N_{xx}(t) + G_{\kappa\ell, yy}(A_{mn}, \varphi_j) N_{yy}(t) + \\ & + G_{\kappa\ell, xy}(A_{mn}, \varphi_j) N_{xy}(t); \quad \kappa, \ell = 1, 2, \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

where the coefficients $G_{\kappa\ell, \gamma\delta}$ are expressed by means of and the elements A_{mn} of the matrix of compliances of the packet according to [7]. Since the elastic constants of the

layer are random values, the elements A_{mn} are also random. As a result, the quality vector $\vec{\varepsilon}^{(j)}(t)$ is the Gaussian random process which depends parametrically on the random values A_{mn} .

The region of the permissible states of the layer Ω_j is supposed in the form of a three-dimensional parallelepiped:

$$\varepsilon_{\kappa\ell}^{** (j)} < \varepsilon_{\kappa\ell}^{(j)}(t) < \varepsilon_{\kappa\ell}^{* (j)} ; \kappa, \ell = 1, 2, \quad (8)$$

where $\varepsilon_{\kappa\ell}^{* (j)}$, $\varepsilon_{\kappa\ell}^{** (j)}$ are random values (the limiting strains of the separate layer). In subsequent considerations, it will be assumed that they are statistically independent and are distributed by the normal law with the given mathematical expectations $\langle \varepsilon_{\kappa\ell}^{(j)} \rangle$, $\langle \varepsilon_{\kappa\ell}^{** (j)} \rangle$ and the rms deviations $\sigma_{\varepsilon_{\kappa\ell}^{* (j)}}$, $\sigma_{\varepsilon_{\kappa\ell}^{** (j)}}$. Thus, the problem of calculating the reliability functions R_j is reduced to calculating the mathematical expectation of the number of intersections by the three-dimensional Gaussian process of the limiting surface with a stochastic boundary Γ_j .

For the highly reliable systems, we can use the formula

$$V(\Gamma_j; t) = \sum_{\kappa, \ell=1, 2} [V_+(\varepsilon_{\kappa\ell}^{* (j)}; t) + V_-(\varepsilon_{\kappa\ell}^{** (j)}; t)], \quad (9)$$

where $V_+(\varepsilon_{\kappa\ell}^{* (j)}; t)$ and $V_-(\varepsilon_{\kappa\ell}^{** (j)}; t)$ are the mathematical expectations of the numbers of intersections per unit time of the positive level $\varepsilon_{\kappa\ell}^{* (j)}$ and the negative level $\varepsilon_{\kappa\ell}^{** (j)}$ accordingly by the random process $\varepsilon_{\kappa\ell}^{(j)}(t)$. The values

$V_+(\varepsilon_{\kappa\ell}^{* (j)}; t)$, $V_-(\varepsilon_{\kappa\ell}^{** (j)}; t)$ are calculated in two stages. Initially, we shall fix the values of the elements A_{mn} of the compliance matrix and calculate the conditional mathematical expectations $V_+(\varepsilon_{\kappa\ell}^{* (j)}; t | A_{mn})$, $V_-(\varepsilon_{\kappa\ell}^{** (j)}; t | A_{mn})$. Subsequently, supposing the elements A_{mn} as the random values, the equation for total probability is used to calculate the unconditional mathematical expectations:

$$V_+(\varepsilon_{\kappa\ell}^{* (j)}; t) = \int \dots \int V_+(\varepsilon_{\kappa\ell}^{* (j)}; t | A_{mn}) p(A_{mn}) dA_{mn}; \quad (10)$$

$$V_-(\varepsilon_{\kappa\ell}^{** (j)}; t) = \int \dots \int V_-(\varepsilon_{\kappa\ell}^{** (j)}; t | A_{mn}) p(A_{mn}) dA_{mn},$$

where $p(A_{mn})$ is the common density of distribution of the elements of the compliance matrix of the packet, and integration is carried out over the entire range of variation of

these elements. The value $p(A_{mn})$ can be determined from the experimentally determined distribution densities of the elastic constants of the layer. For this purpose, it is necessary to use the functional dependences of the elements

on the elastic constants of the layer [7] and the well-known formulas for the law of distribution of a function of a random value. This method is most consistent from the theoretical point of view, but it is associated with complicated problems in practice since the functional relationship between the elastic characteristics and the elements of the compliance matrix of the packet is nonlinear. It should also be mentioned that in literature we have very little amount of experimental data which would make it possible to determine the distribution densities of the elastic characteristics of fiber reinforced composites. These problems can be avoided if it is assumed in advance that the elements A_{mn} are the normal random values which are statistically independent. The mathematical expectation $\langle A_{mn} \rangle$ and dispersion $\sigma_{A_{mn}}^2$ can be determined then using only the numerical characteristics obtained in the experiments from the scatter of the elastic properties, i.e., the general mean and rms deviations. The details are given in [4]. As a final result we obtain the formula for the probability density of the random value

$$p(A_{mn}) = \frac{\exp[-(A_{mn} - \langle A_{mn} \rangle)^2 / 2\sigma_{A_{mn}}^2]}{\sqrt{2\pi} \sigma_{A_{mn}}} \quad (II)$$

The common probability density $p(A_{mn})$ of all the elements of the compliance matrix is the product of the distributions (II). Substituting $p(A_{mn})$ into (IO) and carrying out numerical integration we determine the values $V_+(\epsilon_{kl}^{*(j)}; t)$, $V_-(\epsilon_{kl}^{*(j)}; t)$, and then with respect to formulas (9), (2), (3) calculate the reliability function $R(t)$.

STOCHASTIC MODEL OF LAYER-BY-LAYER FAILURE PROCESS

The formula (3) provides the lower estimate for the reliability function. It is well known that the total exhaustion of the load-carrying capacity of laminated composites

occurs as a result of the complex process of gradual failure in the plies. According to the theory above, if the strain vector $\vec{\epsilon}^{(j)}(t)$ reaches the boundary of the limiting region Ω_j , we shall assume that the j -th ply has failed. But failure (breakdown) may be either partial or total, depending on the type of fracture taking place in the ply, i.e., depending on the type of the component of the quality vector which reaches the limiting value. In partial breakdown, the ply continues to receive part of the load. In complete breakdown, the entire load applied to this ply is redistributed between the remaining plies. As a result of scatter of the limiting strains, the breakdowns of the plies are random events.

On the analogy of the deterministic model of layer-by-layer failure process [8] we assume that in breakdown caused by the shear strains, the ply retains the load-carrying capacity in the direction of fibres and in the transverse direction; if the transverse strain reaches the limiting value, the ply retains its load-carrying capacity as regards to shear stresses and in the direction of fibres; if the strain in the direction of fibres reaches the limiting value, the ply loses completely its load-carrying capacity and all the elastic constants of the ply are assumed to be equal to zero. It should be mentioned that more complicated methods of determining the reduced stiffness of laminated composites during layer-by-layer failure, e.g., the methods proposed in [2], can be used without any large problems.

We consider the laminated composite as a complicated system which goes through a number of states $\mathcal{J}_0, \mathcal{J}_1, \dots$ during the loading process. The transition from one state to another is caused by breakdowns of the plies. If m breakdowns have taken place, we shall assume that the system is in the state \mathcal{J}_m . The transition of the system from one state to another is a random process $\Theta(t)$ which assumes the discrete values $\Theta = \{\mathcal{J}_m; m = 0, 1, \dots\}$. Let it be that the process $\Theta(t)$ satisfies the following conditions:

- I) if the system is in state \mathcal{J}_m at time t , the probability of the $\mathcal{J}_m \rightarrow \mathcal{J}_{m+1}$ transition during a short period of time

- $[t, t + \Delta t]$ is equal to $\lambda_m(t)\Delta t + O(\Delta t)$;
- 2) the probability of retention of the previous state is equal to $1 - \lambda_m(t)\Delta t + O(\Delta t)$;
 - 3) the process is ordinary, i.e., the probability of transition from \mathcal{D}_m to the state differing from \mathcal{D}_{m+1} is $O(\Delta t)$.
- These conditions determine the Markovian process of pure origination, with the transition intensities $\lambda_m(t)$. The probability $p_m(t)$ of the system being in state \mathcal{D}_m is determined by a system of differential equations

$$\frac{d p_m(t)}{d t} = \lambda_{m-1}(t) p_{m-1}(t) - \lambda_m(t) p_m(t); \quad m = 0, 1, \dots; \quad \lambda_{-1} = 0. \quad (I2)$$

If at $t = 0$ the system is in the initial state \mathcal{D}_0 , then

$$p_0(0) = 1; \quad p_m(0) = 0 \text{ for } m \geq 1. \quad (I3)$$

Under the initial conditions (I3), the general solution of the system (I2) is determined by recurrent relationships

$$p_0(t) = \mathcal{M}_0(t); \quad p_m(t) = \mathcal{M}_m(t) \int_0^t \frac{\lambda_{m-1}(\tau)}{\mathcal{M}_m(\tau)} p_{m-1}(\tau) d\tau; \quad m \geq 1, \quad (I4)$$

where $\mathcal{M}_m(t) = \exp\left[-\int_0^t \lambda_m(\tau) d\tau\right]$.

The transition intensities $\lambda_m(t)$ are determined by the type of failure which takes place in the transition of the system from state \mathcal{D}_m to \mathcal{D}_{m+1} . Let it be ξ a random value denoting the time to the breakdown corresponding to the failure form $\xi_{\kappa\ell}^{(j)}(t | \mathcal{D}_m) \geq \xi_{\kappa\ell}^{*(j)}$. This form is related to the function of the intensity of breakdown $\lambda_{\kappa\ell}(t)$ determined as the density of conventional probability of this failure occurring at time t , on the condition that the breakdown of the given type had not taken place prior to this instant:

$$\lambda_{\kappa\ell}(t) = \lim_{\Delta t \rightarrow 0} \frac{P[t \leq \xi \leq t + \Delta t | \xi > t]}{\Delta t}. \quad (I5)$$

The conditional probability $P[A|B]$ may be expressed by means of the distribution function F_{ij} of the time to the start of breakdown of the given type. Carrying out the lim-

iting transition in (I5), we obtain

$$\lambda_{\kappa\ell}(t) = \frac{1}{1 - F_{\kappa\ell}(t)} \frac{dF_{\kappa\ell}(t)}{dt}. \quad (\text{I6})$$

The same procedure is also used to determine the function of the intensity of breakdown corresponding to the failure form $\xi_{\kappa\ell}^{(j)}(t | \mathcal{D}_m) \leq \xi_{\kappa\ell}^{** (j)}$. The equation (I6) can be solved in relation to $F_{\kappa\ell}(t)$. For the condition $F_{\kappa\ell}(0) = 0$, we obtain

$$F_{\kappa\ell}(t) = 1 - \exp\left[-\int_0^t \lambda_{\kappa\ell}(\tau) d\tau\right]. \quad (\text{I7})$$

Let it be that in each state \mathcal{D}_m we can determine the failure form for which the intensity of breakdowns $\lambda_{\kappa\ell}^*(t)$ is maximum at each point of a time range $[0, t_m]$. Consequently, the specified failure form has the maximum probability of realization and, in accordance with the accepted postulate, the transition intensity is $\lambda_m(t) = \lambda_{\kappa\ell}^*(t)$ for $t \in [0, t_m]$. Thus, the problem of the description of the stochastic layer-by-layer failure process is reduced to calculating the intensities of breakdowns $\lambda_{\kappa\ell}^*(t)$ for all the possible forms of failure and to finding the breakdown with the maximum probability of realization. To calculate the functions $\lambda_{\kappa\ell}(t)$ we are to detail the nature of loads acting on the system. Several examples of calculating $\lambda_m(t)$ and $\rho_m(t)$ are given in [5] for laminated composites under deterministic and random loads.

The process of layer-by-layer failure is accompanied by the reduction in the stiffness of the composite and, consequently, by a reduction of its load-carrying capacity. The following procedure can be used to describe this phenomenon. The load-carrying capacity of the composite in the state \mathcal{D}_m is characterized by the damage vector $\vec{\omega}^{(m)} = \{\omega_1^{(m)}; \omega_2^{(m)}; \omega_6^{(m)}\}$, whose components are determined according to the formula $\omega_i^{(m)} = 1 - C_{ii}^{(m)} / C_{ii}^{(o)}$, where $C_{ii}^{(o)}$ and $C_{ii}^{(m)}$ are the components of the matrix of membrane stiffnesses of the packet in the initial state and in the state \mathcal{D}_m . The load-carrying capacity of the composite is completely exhausted if even

only one of the components of the vector $\vec{\omega}^{(m)}$ reaches the value $\omega_i^{(m)} = 1$. It is necessary to take into account the fact that in certain lay-up systems of the plies, the load-carrying capacity of the packet can be exhausted prior to the event that the condition $\omega_i^{(m)} = 1$ is realized. Such a situation associates with the fact that at specific step of layer-by-layer failure the matrix of membrane stiffnesses becomes degenerate, or the matrix of compliances becomes singular (the example for cross-ply composite is given in [5]). This is treated in the model as an alternative condition of the complete exhaustion of the load-carrying capacity.

The state \mathcal{J}_M in which at least one of the components of the damage vector reaches the critical value $\omega_i^{(m)} = 1$ or the stiffness matrix of the packet becomes degenerate will be referred to as a critical state. The reliability of the laminated composite $R(t)$ is evaluated from the probability $p_M(t)$ of establishment of the critical state:

$R(t) = 1 - p_M(t)$. The probability $p_M(t)$ can be calculated easily if it is assumed that in the process $\Theta(t)$ the state \mathcal{J}_M is absorbing, i.e., $\lambda_M = 0$. Then

$$R(t) = 1 - \int_0^t \lambda_{M-1}(\tau) p_{M-1}(\tau) d\tau.$$

The probability model of layer-by-layer failure considered above makes it possible to calculate the reliability function of the laminated composites and composite structures taking into account the scatter of the elastic and strength characteristics of the plies. The loads acting on the composite may be both deterministic and random functions of time.

RELIABILITY OF LAMINATED COMPOSITE CYLINDRICAL SHELLS

Several examples of the practical application of the proposed methods are given in [4,5]. An organic fibre/epoxy circular cylindrical shell produced by the method of continuous filament winding is under consideration. It is assumed that the load is random internal pressure $q(t)$. The numerical results illustrate the effect of the reduction in reliability for a number of different laminated shells

caused by:

- 1) stochastic character of the load;
- 2) the scatter of elastic constants of the lamina;
- 3) the scatter of limiting strains of the lamina.

The results indicate that the third factor is more important than the second one. The analysis of layer-by-layer failure shows that the strength scatter changes in certain cases the dominating failure mode in the lamina and influences strongly the critical state \mathcal{I}_M . The results illustrate also a scale effect of reliability. Using the criteria of the first -ply-failure, we obtain a monotonic reduction of reliability with an increase in the number of plies. When using the criterion of complete exhaustion of the load-carrying capacity for high reliability values, the scale effect indicates a qualitatively different nature, i.e., reliability increases with increasing number of plies.

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